

Overhead Quantification of the Lightweight Distributed Metric Service for High-Performance Computers

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Abstract—The Lightweight Distributed Metric Service (LDMS) is a monitoring framework that collects high-fidelity, high-volume node-level data on large distributed computer systems. LDMS is built to introduce negligible overhead in application workloads which has been verified in several scale tests since its inception in 2014. However, new communication strategies, sensor samplers, and fundamental data structures within the core LDMS code have been introduced that could increase the overhead. In this study, we quantify the current overhead that LDMS introduces and verify that it is insignificant. This was done through a variety of benchmarks and applications where we captured timing and performance statistics while LDMS ran with different configurations.

I. INTRODUCTION

The modern world of high-performance computing (HPC) is made up of a variety of workloads from artificial intelligence (AI) to computational physics. These intense workloads demand system and application monitoring data in order to debug, increase performance, and gain insight into overall system health. The Lightweight Distributed Metric Service (LDMS) is an "always-on" monitoring tool that aims to collect continuous data on application performance and system conditions. It was first introduced in 2014 by a Sandia National Laboratories-led team and has since been deployed on systems across the DOE/NNSA laboratories and around the world [1]. A main priority for LDMS is that it remains lightweight, adding little overhead and impact on application performance for users.

LDMS is able to gather system-wide data efficiently through multi-threaded daemons that can be used for sampling or aggregation [1]. Samplers query a variety of hardware performance counters and then store them into a single metric set. Aggregators then collect these metric sets from samplers and/or other aggregators. A different set of aggregators then uploads the metric sets to a database which can then be used for analysis or visualization tools such as Grafana.

Over the past decade, the tool has evolved to support more samplers and gather data from tools such as Kokkos. Additionally, applications have evolved in their computing demands

and overall complexity. To ensure that LDMS continues to be utilized, it is necessary to quantify the overhead that LDMS introduces again to get more accurate data to workloads today. These results will help influence system administrative decisions on the data frequency collection for application and system level health. In this paper, we will explain the selection of four different benchmarks we used in this study and present our findings of overhead for each. We will summarize the results and analyze the overhead that can be expected when deploying LDMS.

II. METHODOLOGY

The overarching goal of this research was to get a comprehensive analysis at how LDMS affects different workloads. We also analyzed how changing the frequency of data collection affected performance. We chose two benchmarks (HPL and HPL-MxP) and two "real world" simulations (SNAP and Empire). Each one was chosen specifically to represent real workloads in the modern era. With these tests, we have created a robust representation of applications while keeping in mind that further testing with more benchmarks and applications could be done.

The tests were run on single nodes in order to best isolate resources to provide a controlled environment, free from external disruptions. We also chose tests that do little to no writing to the shared filesystem. This was done to minimize runtime variability caused by other users writing to the filesystem simultaneously. Additionally, in order to obtain a baseline performance, applications were optimized to the point of having expected results for the respective code and then the same variables were used for each test. For example, the expected results of the SNAP application when tested on Intel Xeon Haswell processors can achieve a grind time (the figure of merit for the test) of 7.02E-1 nanoseconds [4]. We used a hyper-threaded Intel Xeon Platinum 8268 (Cascade Lake) CPU with 48 cores were able to produce a mean grind time of 7.95E-1 nanoseconds with LDMS turned off. We considered this result valid, as it was within a reasonable expected amount for our system. This was then used for the rest of our tests, serving as our control groups.

All tests were run with **LDMS** on and off at a sampling frequency of 1s. Experiments with **LDMS** on, off, and at different sampling frequencies (1s, 20s, and 60s) were also done to quantify the impact on application runtimes. For testing the sampling frequencies, we chose to only run the Empire test as it inherently had the least amount of OS level noise.

A. HPL

The High-Performance LINPACK (HPL) benchmark performs dense matrix multiplication and measures a system’s performance in the amount of floating point operations it can do in seconds [2]. HPL serves as a key benchmark in determining the Top500 [3] supercomputers but is exclusively a measurement of floating point operation peak potential, not a holistic test of all HPC subsystems.

B. HPL-MxP

The HPL Mixed-Precision (HPL-MxP) benchmark solves a large dense matrix problem with iterative refinement using mixed precision [4]. This method effectively emulates the behavior of AI and HPC workloads. Specifically, we chose this benchmark so we could test a GPU configuration on a simulative AI workload. The benchmark was run on 4 NVIDIA H100 SXM5 GPUs, using NVIDIA’s HPL-MxP distribution [6]. Similar to HPL, the figure of merit is GFLOP/s and today is often measured in TeraFLOP/s (TFLOP/s).

C. SNAP

SNAP is a proxy application developed by Los Alamos National Laboratory (LANL) that solves a structured mesh, linear radiation pseudo-transport problem [5]. The code was written in modern Fortran, the only benchmark in our set to do so. SNAP mimics the computational workload, memory requirements, and communication pattern of a computational physics application.

D. Empire

Empire is a Sandia-developed plasma physics Particle In Cell (PIC) code that is written in modern C++ on top of the Kokkos performance portability framework. This allows Empire to be performant on various hardware without needing code changes. We did not use a formal benchmark but an actual test from the Empire suite. The test begins real physics simulation from the first time step, an advantage over other typical PIC simulation tests that start with a quiescent state.

III. RESULTS

Tests for each configuration of **LDMS** were ran at least 200 times to ensure statistical validity. For each configuration, the average performance (based on the figure of merit, where applicable) and time were calculated along with the variance of the mean to drive down the error in the average. The majority of the benchmarks were ran on Sandia’s Jetcool system which is comprised of 32 nodes featuring Intel Xeon Platinum 8268 (Cascade Lake) CPUs with 48 cores that are hyperthreaded to

TABLE I
AVERAGE RUNTIME: UNMONITORED AND MONITORED

Applications	LDMS		
	Off (s)	On (s)	Difference (s)
HPL	958.018 ± 89.558	958.111 ± 87.049	-0.19
HPL-MxP	86.185 ± 74.061	81.685 ± 111.865	+4.50
Empire	107.919 ± 0.0276	107.911 ± 0.0351	+0.00890
SNAP	192.15 ± 18.410	191.96 ± 18.461	+0.190

^aDifference is calculated as unmonitored subtracted from monitored.

Fig. 1. The average runtimes (in seconds) for the Empire simulation over 200 samples with **LDMS** off and then at varying sampling frequencies. The y-axis does not start at zero to emphasize the miniscule difference in runtimes across the frequencies.

allow programs to use up to 96 CPUs. HPL-MxP as mentioned above utilized a GPU cluster instead.

The difference in runtimes with **LDMS** turned on and off for HPL, the Empire simulation, and SNAP was within milliseconds of each other as seen in Table 1. The largest difference was in the HPL-MxP benchmark, which had a faster runtime with LDMS turned on than off. However, it should be noted that this benchmark had a significantly high variance ($\pm 74.061s$, $\pm 111.865s$) so this does not necessarily mean it runs faster when **LDMS** is turned on. Additionally, varying the sampling frequency (Fig. 1) had an insignificant effect on runtime. It is expected that as the sampling frequency goes up, the runtime would increase but we have demonstrated that this change is miniscule.

IV. CONCLUSION

In this study, we conducted a thorough analysis of the Lightweight Distributed Metric Service (**LDMS**) and its impact on the runtime performance of various high-performance computing (HPC) applications. Our findings indicate that **LDMS** introduces differences in runtime and figures of merit within fractions of a percent compared to an unmonitored system. This minimal overhead underscores the effectiveness of **LDMS** as a low-overhead monitoring tool. The work conducted in this study not only reinforces the credibility of **LDMS** but also encourages its adoption across various computational workloads, particularly in scenarios where monitoring is crucial for performance tuning and system health assessment.

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